

ISic4414

Epitaph for Eupolemos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited museum

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 32 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Museo Archeologico Santi Furnari di Tripi, inventory ME23438

Physical Description

Stele of the local stone, damaged below, forming part of an epymbion ('type B')

Dimensions

Height 51.5 cm

Width 30.5 cm

Depth 14.5 cm

Layout

Single line of Greek letters filling the width of the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plain letters carved in a deep square cut: E has shorter mid-bar; upsilon slightly exceeds the line; pi is wide and square in form, with fractionally shorter right hasta; omicron is only slightly smaller than the other letters; mu has vertical first and last strokes, while the mid-strokes descend less than half-way.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Εὐπολέμου

Apparatus

text of Sofia 2018

Translation (en)

(Tomb) of Eupolemos

Commentary

The name Eupolemos [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=%CE%95%CE%A5%CE%A0%CE%9F%CE%9B]

%CE%95%CE%9C%CE%9F%CE%A3] is a common one, with at last seven other attestations on the island, all from eastern Sicily.

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4414>

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Bibliography

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